

A survey about your diabetes service (xx)

* Required

Section 1: Demographic information and organisational context

This first section of the survey will inform our understanding of different DAFNE centres and will not be discussed in the tailoring session so please feel free to respond openly and honestly.

1. Discipline/Profession *

Mark only one oval.

- Clinical nurse specialist
- Consultant endocrinologist
- Dietician
- Administrator
- Other: _____

2. Further qualifications (please tick all that apply) *

Check all that apply.

- Higher diploma
- Master's degree
- Doctoral degree or equivalent
- None
- Other: _____

3. How many years of experience do you have providing diabetes care? *

Mark only one oval.

- 0-6 months
- 7-11 months
- 1 to 2 years
- 3 to 5 years
- 6-10 years
- Over 10 years

4. How long have you been in your present job? *

Mark only one oval.

- 0-6 months
- 7-11 months
- 1 to 2 years
- 3 to 5 years
- 6-10 years
- Over 10 years

5. Have you completed the DAFNE training programme?

Check all that apply.

- Yes
- No

6. If yes, have you delivered a DAFNE course?

Check all that apply.

- Yes
- No
- N/A

7. If yes, in what format have you delivered the DAFNE course?

Mark only one oval.

- In-person
- Online
- Both In-person & Online
- N/A

8. Do you have any further comments on your training and experience in DAFNE?

Organisational context

Through the next set of questions below, we want to understand the culture and climate in your diabetes service and whether it is supportive of implementation. When answering these questions, think about your diabetes service.

9. Culture *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
People at all levels openly talk about what is and is not working	<input type="radio"/>				
Most people in the diabetes service are willing to change how they do things in response to feedback from others	<input type="radio"/>				
It is hard to get things to change in our diabetes service	<input type="radio"/>				
I can rely on the other people in this diabetes service to do their jobs well	<input type="radio"/>				
Most of the people who work in our diabetes service seem to enjoy their work	<input type="radio"/>				
Difficult problems are solved through face-	<input type="radio"/>				

to-face discussions

We regularly take time to reflect on how we do things

After trying something new, we take time to think about how it worked

10. Culture stress *

Mark only one oval per row.

Strongly disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

I am under too many pressures to do my job effectively

Staff members often show signs of stress and strain

The heavy workload here reduces program effectiveness

Staff frustration is common here

11. Culture effort *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
People in this diabetes service always want to perform to the best of their abilities	<input type="radio"/>				
People are enthusiastic about their work	<input type="radio"/>				
People in our diabetes service get by with doing as little as possible	<input type="radio"/>				
People are prepared to make a special effort to do a good job	<input type="radio"/>				
People in this diabetes service do not put more effort into their work than they have to	<input type="radio"/>				

12. Implementation culture *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Staff within the diabetes service are expected to help the DAFNE programme meet its goal	<input type="radio"/>				
Staff within the diabetes service get the support they need to implement the DAFNE programme	<input type="radio"/>				
Staff within the diabetes service get recognition for implementing DAFNE programme to improve diabetes care	<input type="radio"/>				
The DAFNE programme to improve diabetes care is a top priority of the diabetes service	<input type="radio"/>				

13. Learning climate *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
We regularly take time to consider ways to improve how we do things	<input type="radio"/>				
People in our diabetes service actively seek new ways to improve how we do things	<input type="radio"/>				
This diabetes service encourages everyone to share ideas	<input type="radio"/>				
This diabetes service learns from its mistakes	<input type="radio"/>				
When we experience a problem in the diabetes service, we make a serious effort to figure out what's really going on	<input type="radio"/>				

14. Available resources *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
In general, when there is agreement that change needs to happen in the diabetes service, we have the necessary support in terms of budget or financial resources	<input type="radio"/>				
In general, when there is agreement that change needs to happen in the diabetes service, we have the necessary support in terms of training	<input type="radio"/>				
In general, when there is agreement that change needs to happen in the diabetes service, we have the necessary support in terms of staffing	<input type="radio"/>				
The following are	<input type="radio"/>				

**available to make
DAFNE work in our
diabetes service:
equipment and
materials**

**The following are
available to make
DAFNE work in our
diabetes service:
patient
awareness/need**

**The following are
available to make
DAFNE work in our
diabetes service:
provider buy-in**

**The following are
available to make
DAFNE work in our
diabetes service:
intervention team**

Leadership engagement

We recognise that leadership happens at many levels. However, for the purposes of this survey we are focusing on clinical leadership as represented by consultant(s) within the diabetes service. Therefore, if you are in this role, please be aware that you may be answering this set of questions about yourself.

15. Leadership *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
The diabetes service leadership makes sure that we have the time and space necessary to discuss changes to improve care	<input type="radio"/>				
Leadership in this diabetes service creates an environment where things can be accomplished	<input type="radio"/>				
Diabetes service leadership promotes an environment that is an enjoyable place to work	<input type="radio"/>				
Leadership strongly supports diabetes service change efforts	<input type="radio"/>				

16. Do you have any further comments on culture, climate, resources, and leadership within your diabetes service?

Section 2: Factors which might influence the implementation of DAFNE at your centre

The answers provided in this section of the survey will be used to inform our discussions during the tailoring session.

Following a review of the literature, we have determined some factors that might help (enabler) or hinder (barrier) the implementation of DAFNE.

Please consider each factor and indicate whether it is a barrier or enabler in your DAFNE centre.

17. Available resources *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Barrier at my centre	Enabler at my centre	Neither
Administrative support	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Funding	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Number of clinical staff	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Recruitment of clinical staff	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Space/venues (adequacy)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Space/venues (availability)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online referral system	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

18. Access to knowledge and information *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Barrier at my centre	Enabler at my centre	Neither
Access to staff training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Logistics of arranging group staff training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Brevity of training	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Time lag between training and delivery	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Staff confidence in course content	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Level of staff preparation (course content)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Staff familiarity with course content	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Time required to prepare for sessions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Staff knowledge of participants	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

19. Networking, communication, leadership *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Barrier at my centre	Enabler at my centre	Neither
Long-standing relationships between staff members	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reputation of programme founders	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Consultant involvement	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Whole team dedication	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Hospital champions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

20. Process of implementing the programme *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Barrier at my centre	Enabler at my centre	Neither
Reminder letters	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Participant recruitment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Coordinating dates, times, and room bookings	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Managing (class) group dynamics	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Running sessions on time	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Participant retention	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

21. If some of these factors were neither a barrier nor enabler, please briefly explain

22. Are there other factors that help or hinder the implementation of DAFNE at your centre?

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